

Liquid membrane phenomena : characterization of liquid membranes generated by binary mixtures of surfactants[†]

Abhay K. Jain* and Jai P. Upadhyay

Chemistry Department, D.D.U. Gorakhpur University, Gorakhpur-273 009, Inida

E-mail : jain_ak00@hotmail.com Fax : 91-551-2340459

Manuscript received 11 September 2002

The transport behavior of liquid membranes generated by Triton X-100-cholesterol mixture at sintered glass membrane-water interface has been studied. Data on ordinary permeability, electroosmotic velocity, streaming potential and streaming current have been used to calculate the transport coefficients. Attempt has also been made to evaluate the transport coefficients accounting for liquid membranes alone. The results are indicative of the applicability of liquid membranes as a model system for biological membranes.

It is generally believed that thin films in aqueous medium exist in liquid state. The correctness of this assumption is attested by Kesting's liquid membrane hypothesis¹, which was originally formulated to explain the enhance salt rejection due to addition of surfactant to saline feed in reverse osmosis. Its extension to the system of biophysical interest has been attempted²⁻⁵. The Kesting's liquid membrane hypothesis further postulated that as the concentration of surfactant is increased, the interface gets progressively covered with surfactant liquid membrane. At the critical micelle concentration (CMC) coverage of the interface with the liquid membrane is complete. Experimental evidences furnished additional support in favor of progressive coverage²⁻⁴. However, in some cases progressive coverage exceeds monolayer capacity and generates multilayer at the interface⁵⁻⁸.

It was shown in an earlier communication⁶ that liquid membranes generated by binary mixture of surfactants are stabilized when surfactants attain definite concentration in the dispersion. Also, the liquid membranes generated in this way serve as model systems for biological membranes⁶⁻⁹. Hence it appears worthwhile to study transport behavior of liquid membranes generated by binary mixture of surfactants.

It has been investigated¹⁰⁻¹⁴ that cholesterol and Triton X-100 are very effective surfactants of biological significance, when added to the water generate surfactant layer liquid membranes at the interface. The experiments on electroosmotic transport reported in this communication have been undertaken to demonstrate the existence of liquid membranes generated by cholesterol-Triton X-100 mixture. The transport data have been analyzed using the theory of

thermodynamics of irreversible processes (TIP)¹⁵ with a view to evaluate the transport coefficients accounting for liquid membrane alone. The results presented herein appear pertinent, particularly in generating membrane mimetic models.

The analysis of the data indicates that the stabilization of liquid membranes at the interface occurs when both surfactants reach near their CMC values. Moreover, the results obtained corroborate the existence of liquid membranes generated by the mixture of cholesterol and Triton X-100 at the interface.

Results and discussion

The linear phenomenological relations for the simultaneous transport of matter and electricity, as obtained from non-equilibrium thermodynamic treatment of electroosmotic effects^{15,16}, can be written as

$$J_v = L_{11}\Delta P + L_{12}\Delta\phi \quad (1)$$

$$I = L_{21}\Delta P + L_{22}\Delta\phi \quad (2)$$

where J_v is the volume flux, I the flow of electricity, and ΔP and $\Delta\phi$ are the pressure difference and electrical potential difference, respectively. The coefficients L_{ik} are called the phenomenological coefficients and following equality

$$L_{12} = L_{21} \quad (3)$$

among them holds on account of Onsager's theorem. From eqns. (1) and (2), the following equalities can be deduced :

$$(J_v)_{\Delta\phi=0} = L_{11}\Delta P \text{ (for ordinary permeability)} \quad (4)$$

$$(J_v)_{\Delta P=0} = L_{12}\Delta P \text{ (for electroosmotic velocity)} \quad (5)$$

[†]Dedicated to Professor R. P. Rastogi.

$$(\Delta\phi/\Delta P)_{I=0} = -L_{21}/L_{22} \text{ (for streaming potential)} \quad (6)$$

$$(I)_{\Delta\phi=0} = L_{21}\Delta P \text{ (for streaming current)} \quad (7)$$

which all predict straight line plots passing through origin. The data on ordinary permeability, electroosmotic velocity, streaming potential and streaming current obtained when concentration of cholesterol was varied in dispersion holding the concentrations of Triton X-100 constant at CMC have been plotted in Figs. 1–4. Similar plots were obtained when concentration of Triton X-100 was varied holding the concentration of cholesterol constant at CMC. In all cases straight line plots are obtained in accordance with eqns. (4)–(7).

Fig. 1. Ordinary permeability data for various compositions of Triton X-100 and cholesterol in the case when cholesterol was varied and Triton X-100 kept constant at CMC.

The values of various phenomenological coefficients, viz. L_{11} , L_{12} , L_{21} and L_{22} for all composition of mixtures estimated from the slopes of above mentioned plots are recorded in Table 1. It is worth to mention that the maximum error, calculated from the estimates of various errors, in experimentally determined values was within the limit of $\pm 5.0\%$. The validity of ORR for all compositions is obvious from Table 1.

It can be seen from Table 1 and from Figs. 5 and 6 that if cholesterol is added to the solution of Triton X-100 of

Fig. 2. Electroosmotic velocity data for various compositions as in Fig. 1.

concentration equal to its CMC, the L_{ik} coefficients decrease and go on decreasing with increasing concentration of cholesterol. An obvious implication of this observation is that the decrease in L_{ik} values is due to incorporation of added cholesterol in Triton X-100 liquid membranes, which already exists at the interface. This observation is consistent with earlier results obtained on phospholipid cholesterol¹⁷ and lecithin-cholesterol mixtures⁶. Wherein decreasing water permeability with increasing concentration of cholesterol has been attributed to the fact that cholesterol strengthens the hydrophobic core and increases its viscosity. Another plausible reason which must be looked into is the possibility of formation of multilayers⁶ at the interface by surfactant-surfactant interactions and hydrogen bonding between hydroxyl groups of cholesterol¹⁸.

The spontaneous orientation of surfactant molecules at the interface leads to a reduction of interfacial energy and is of fundamental importance in the formation of molecular aggregates and thin films, which persist in liquid state¹⁹. Thus liquid membranes form spontaneously even without impingement as a result of surfactant capacity of dissolved molecules¹. Surface activity is, of course, related to the hydrophilic/hydrophobic balance of these molecules. Because of the surface active nature of both Triton X-100⁶

Fig. 3. Streaming potential data for various compositions as in Fig. 1.

Fig. 4. Streaming current data for various compositions as in Fig. 1.

Table 1. Values of various phenomenological coefficients (L_{ik}) for liquid membranes generated by Triton X-100-cholesterol mixtures

Composition			$\times 10^{12} L_{11}$	$\times 10^{10} L_{12}$	$\times 10^{10} L_{21}$	$\times 10^4 L_{22}$
Triton X-100	+	Cholesterol	$m^5 N^{-1} s^{-1}$	$m^3 AJ^{-1}$	$m^3 AJ^{-1}$	AV^{-1}
$10^{-5} M$		nM				
(a) When concentration of Triton X-100 was kept constant at CMC $30 \times 10^{-5} M$ and concentration of cholesterol solution varied						
0.00	+	0.00	1.360	2.660	2.620	0.268
30.0	+	0.00	0.609	1.085	1.078	0.146
30.0	+	10.0	0.496	0.875	0.865	0.106
30.0	+	20.0	0.446	0.615	0.610	0.086
30.0	+	30.0	0.420	0.500	0.508	0.078
30.0	+	35.0	0.416	0.455	0.458	0.071
30.0	+	40.0	0.394	0.460	0.464	0.065
(b) When concentration cholesterol was kept constant at CMC 30 nM and concentration of Triton X-100 solution varied						
0.00	+	30.0	0.903	0.985	0.987	0.130
10.0	+	30.0	0.693	0.745	0.748	0.112
20.0	+	30.0	0.560	0.610	0.608	0.094
30.0	+	30.0	0.420	0.500	0.508	0.078
35.0	+	30.0	0.396	0.425	0.429	0.065
40.0	+	30.0	0.380	0.390	0.394	0.061

Fig. 5. Variation of L_{ik} coefficients with concentration of Triton X-100 when cholesterol concentration was kept constant at CMC.

and cholesterol¹⁰ it is natural to expect that in the liquid membranes generated by Triton X-100-cholesterol mixtures, the hydrophobic ends of molecules will preferentially oriented towards the supporting membrane and hydrophilic ends will be drawn outwards away from the supporting membrane. Liquid membranes generated in this way form composite structure with supporting membrane with which they act in series.

In such situations the lowering of interfacial energy is consistent with the fact that adsorption also occurs spontaneously. Since interfacial energy decreases with increase in concentration, the adsorption is expected to increase to the extent that exceeds monolayer capacity of the interfacial surface. In this situation, a model based on multilayer is indicative²⁰. Though physical existence of these layers arranged in series can not be distinguished in our macroscopic transport experiments, qualitatively their contribution in increasing the resistance is not too insignificant to be ignored (Table 2). The values of the R_{ik} coefficient (Table 2) were obtained by transforming L_{ik} coefficients into R_{ik} coefficients using the relation¹⁵,

$$R_{ik} = \frac{A_{ik}}{|L|} \quad (8)$$

A_{ik} being the minor of L_{ik} and $|L|$ the determinant of L_{ik} .

In view of the foregoing discussion, the successive growth of liquid membrane layers with increasing concentration offer greater resistance to flow (Table 2) and consequently L_{ik} coefficients show decreasing trend. Similar consideration would explain the progressive diminution in the values of L_{ik} coefficients when the concentration of Triton X-100 is increased in the dispersion holding the concentration of cholesterol constant at CMC.

In dealing with composite series membrane it is more convenient to utilize inverse phenomenological relations between thermodynamic fluxes and forces¹⁵. Based on

Fig. 6. Variation of L_{ik} coefficients with concentration of cholesterol when Triton X-100 was kept constant at CMC.

formalism developed by Kedem and Katchalsky²¹ for the composite series membrane, we can write relationship between the coefficients representing the series membrane as a whole and those of its constituent membrane elements as

$$R_{ik} = \sum_{\Gamma} R_{ik}^{\Gamma} \quad (9)$$

It is plausible to consider under the present experimental conditions that the series membrane generated consists of two membrane elements, viz. the supporting membrane and one unit layer of liquid membrane generated by Triton X-100-cholesterol mixture. The form of eqn. (9) in the

present case can be expressed as

$$R_{ik}^T = R_{ik}^l + R_{ik}^g \quad (10)$$

where superscripts *T*, *l* and *g* stand for total series membrane, liquid membranes and supporting membrane, respectively.

Functionally, R_{ik}^g are the values corresponding to 0.0

concentration (Table 2) and R_{ik}^T the values corresponding to concentration of surfactants in mixture at which R_{ik}^l values are to be evaluated. The values of R_{ik}^l calculated from eqn. (10) are recorded in Table 3. For liquid membranes alone the validity of ORR is obvious from Table 3. The decreasing trend of R_{ik}^l with increasing concentration of surfactant in the dispersion supports the idea of progressive coverage of

Table 2. Values of resistance coefficients (R_{ik}) for liquid membranes in series with supporting membrane

Composition						
Triton X-100 $10^{-5} M$	+	Cholesterol nM	$\times 10^{-12} R_{11}$ $m^{-5} NS$	$\times 10^{-6} R_{12}$ $m^{-3} A^{-1}J$	$\times 10^{-6} R_{21}$ $m^{-3} A^{-1}J$	$\times 10^{-4} \times R_{22}$ $A^{-1}V$
(a) When concentration of Triton X-100 was kept constant at CMC $30 \times 10^{-5} M$ and concentration of cholesterol solution varied						
0.00	+	0.00	0.735 ^a	7.312 ^a	7.203 ^a	3.731 ^a
30.0	+	0.00	1.642	12.219	12.141	6.849
30.0	+	10.0	2.016	16.666	16.476	9.434
30.0	+	20.0	2.242	16.049	15.919	11.627
30.0	+	30.0	2.381	15.274	15.535	12.821
30.0	+	35.0	2.404	15.415	15.525	14.085
30.0	+	40.0	2.538	17.976	18.133	15.385
(b) When concentration of cholesterol was kept constant at CMC 30 nM and concentration of Triton X-100 solution varied						
0.00	+	30.0	1.107	8.397	8.415	7.692
10.0	+	30.0	1.443	9.605	9.652	8.928
20.0	+	30.0	1.786	11.596	11.558	10.638
30.0	+	30.0	2.381	15.274	15.535	12.821
35.0	+	30.0	2.525	16.523	16.678	15.385
40.0	+	30.0	2.632	16.836	17.008	16.393

^aCorresponding to R_{ik}^g values.

Table 3. Values of various R_{ik} coefficients accounting for liquid membranes alone

Composition of						
Triton X-100 $10^{-5} M$	+	Cholesterol nM	$\times 10^{-12} R_{11}^l$ $m^{-5} NS$	$\times 10^{-6} R_{12}^l$ $m^{-3} A^{-1}J$	$\times 10^{-6} R_{21}^l$ $m^{-3} A^{-1}J$	$\times 10^{-4} R_{22}^l$ $A^{-1}V$
(a) When concentration of Triton X-100 was kept constant at CMC $30 \times 10^{-5} M$ and concentration of cholesterol solution varied						
30.0	+	0.00	0.907	4.907	4.938	3.118
30.0	+	10.0	1.281	9.354	9.273	5.703
30.0	+	20.0	1.507	8.737	8.716	7.897
30.0	+	30.0	1.646	7.962	8.332	9.090
30.0	+	35.0	1.669	8.103	8.322	10.354
30.0	+	40.0	1.803	10.664	10.930	11.654
(b) When concentration of cholesterol was kept constant at CMC 30 nM and concentration of Triton X-100 solution varied						
0.00	+	30.0	0.372	1.086	1.213	3.731
10.0	+	30.0	0.408	2.293	2.449	5.197
20.0	+	30.0	1.051	4.284	4.355	6.907
30.0	+	30.0	1.646	7.962	8.332	9.090
35.0	+	30.0	1.789	9.211	9.475	11.654
40.0	+	30.0	1.897	9.524	9.805	12.662

the supporting membrane. It has been hinted elsewhere^{2,3} that the complete coverage of the supporting membrane occurs when surfactant reach CMC value. In the present case, concentration of one of the surfactants was kept constant at CMC while that of the other surfactant was varied. It was expected that the R_{ik} values should not decrease with change of concentration beyond CMC. The decreasing trend obtained in the present studies further corroborates the formation of multilayer at the supporting membrane water interface⁵⁻⁸.

In conclusion, liquid membranes generated in the present study have water permeability lower than that reported for BLM¹¹ but closer to that for biomembranes¹⁷. Values of electrical resistance of freely formed bilayers in general are much higher¹¹ than that for biomembranes^{11,17}. Liquid membranes formed in this study have values of electrical resistance comparable with those reported for biomembranes^{6,11,14,17}. This indicates the applicability of membranes as model for biomembranes.

Experimental

Cholesterol (Sigma) was recrystallized from absolute ethanol before use. Triton X-100 (C.D.H., India; contained 9.5 oxyethylene group on average as reported by the manufacturer) was used without further treatment. Distilled water, distilled once over potassium permanganate, was used for preparation of aqueous dispersion of cholesterol, Triton X-100 and their mixtures. The method used for preparation of aqueous dispersion was similar to that described earlier⁵. The CMC of the surfactants was determined by the reported method⁵⁻⁷. The CMC of cholesterol and Triton X-100 was found $\sim 30 \pm 0.5$ nM and $\sim 30 \pm 0.5 \times 10^{-5}$ M, respectively, which fairly agreed with that reported earlier^{2,13}.

An all-glass horizontal electroosmotic transport cell used in the present investigation was similar to that described earlier^{5,22,23}. The methods for measurement of ordinary permeability, electroosmotic velocity, streaming potential and streaming current have already been described earlier⁵. Sintered glass membrane (porosity G4) of thickness 2.43×10^{-3} m and area 7.74×10^{-4} m², which separated the transport cell into two compartments, was used to support liquid membranes. All the measurements were made at constant temperature by placing the electroosmotic cell in a thermostat maintained at $38 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

In the present studies, liquid membranes were generated only on one side of the supporting membrane. To achieve this, one side of the supporting membrane (say compartment I^{5,22}) was filled with surfactant solution of desired concentration and other side of the supporting membrane (say compartment II^{5,22}) was filled with water. In all sets of

experiment monitoring of solutions and water filled in electroosmotic cell was done with a conductivity meter to note aging of the solution and, if any change of conductance was noted, the solution was replaced by fresh aqueous solution of the same concentration. Since the conductivity of water in compartment II was never changed during the course of transport experiments, it was believed that only water was transported through liquid membranes. This is in conformity with our earlier finding⁵⁻⁸.

Acknowledgement

This work forms part of a programme sponsored by U.G.C., New Delhi. One of the authors (J.P.U.) is grateful for financial support received in the form of Project Fellow.

References

1. R. E. Kesting, W. J. Subcasky and J. D. Paton, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 1968, **28**, 156.
2. R. C. Srivastava and R. P. S. Jakhar, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1981, **85**, 1437.
3. R. C. Srivastava and R. P. S. Jakhar, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1982, **86**, 1441.
4. A. K. Jain, R. K. Tewari and R. K. Srivastava, *J. Membrane Sci.*, 1987, **31**, 195.
5. A. K. Jain and R. K. Srivastava, *J. Membrane Sci.*, 1990, **51**, 337.
6. A. K. Jain and R. K. Srivastava, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 1991, **145**, 447.
7. A. K. Jain and R. K. Srivastava, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1991, **30**, 7.
8. A. K. Jain, R. K. Srivastava and C. Prasad, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1992, **31**, 569.
9. R. C. Srivastava, "Liquid Membrane Phenomena Biological Implications", Indian Society for Surface Science and Technology, Kolkata, 2002.
10. J. H. Fendler, "Membrane Mimetic Chemistry", Wiley, New York, 1982.
11. H. T. Tien, "Bilayer Lipid Membranes", Marcel Dekker, New York, 1974.
12. R. Jha and J. C. Ahluwalia, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1991, **95**, 7782.
13. T. Liu, R. Guo and G. Song, *J. Dispersion Sci. Technol.*, 1999, **20**, 1205.
14. A. K. Jain and J. P. Upadhyay, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, communicated.
15. A. Katchasky and S. R. Caplan, "Non-equilibrium Thermodynamics in Biophysics", Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 1965.
16. S. R. de Groot, "Thermodynamics of Irreversible Processes", North Holland, Amsterdam, 1966.

17. M. K. Jain, "The Bimolecular Lipid Membranes", Von Nostrand-Reinhold, New York, 1972.
18. J. M. Boggs, *Biochim. Biophys. Acta.* 1987, **906**, 353.
19. R. E. Kesting, "Synthetic Polymeric Membranes", McGraw Hill, New York, 1971.
20. P. C. Hiemenz, "Principles of Colloid and Surface Chemistry", Dekker, New York, 1977.
21. O. Kedem and A. Katchalsky, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1963, **59**, 1941.
22. A. K. Jain, R. K. Srivastava, M. K. Gupta and S. K. Das, *J. Membrane Sci.*, 1993, **78**, 53.
23. A. K. Jain and R. K. Srivastava, *J. Membrane Sci.*, 1996, **112**, 41.

